

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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ANNOTATION. This article discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.

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In today's developing period, changes and significant progress are being made in every field, especially in the field of science. After our country gained independence, attention to science, especially foreign languages, increased. Teaching every subject using modern innovative technologies and methods is one of the most important requirements of today's era. Also, after the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov made a number of decisions on teaching and learning foreign languages, a new environment and era began in our country. [1:46] According to the decision, modern textbooks, methods and technologies were produced. In today's modern education, the demand for interactive methods, innovative technologies, and information technologies to support the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in contrast to traditional education until now, when using modern methods, the necessary conditions are being created for the development, formation, and education of the student's personality. The place and role of modern methods and innovative technologies is huge. There are several effective ways to teach foreign languages, especially English. In particular, in the course of the lesson, you can use video clips, dialogues, movies or cartoons, tape recorders and CDs, which are considered a more traditional method. The use of these technical tools ensures that the process of learning a foreign language is more interesting and effective for students. The importance of modern methods in teaching a foreign language is incomparable. In this place, several methods that are widely used nowadays are being used. For example: [4:62,68]

1. "W-W-W" (we know, we want to know, we know) method. This method is a necessary method for increasing students' understanding of the text and the ability to analyze it during the lesson.

2. Brainstorming is a method of generating ideas. The essence of this method is to divide students' problem-solving processes based on team cooperation into several stages in time: generating ideas, developing them in a critical and constructive manner.

3. Creative Problem Solving. To use this method, the beginning part of the story is read and it is referred to the judgment of the students to find its final part. This method helps the student to develop thinking ability.

4. Quick answers in this case, students are asked a question about the topic. This method serves to increase the efficiency of the lesson.

5. "Pantomime" (Pantomime) - explaining different words through gestures. This method is suitable for the purpose when it is used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when students are tired after doing written exercises.

6. "A chain story" - a story is told. This method develops oral speech of students.

7. The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps in teaching English and developing oral speech of students. For this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic. [6:153]

8. "Quiz cards" - in which cards are distributed according to the number of students and ensures that all students participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves a lot of time.

9. "Cluster" method. Clustering is a pedagogical strategy that helps students think freely and openly about a topic. This method is basically an effective method for awakening new ideas and adding new ideas to existing knowledge.

10. "Insert" method. In this, students are presented with a text or story and asked to retell it. This method is a powerful way to support engagement, attention, and comprehension when working with text.

So, as shown above, each method has effective methods for teaching foreign languages. Effective use of modern pedagogical technologies and methods in each lesson during the teaching process helps students to think independently and freely, to search, to take a serious approach to every issue, to strengthen their interest in learning. both can achieve positive results. [8:178,181]

In conclusion, in today's rapidly developing era, in a time when the need to teach foreign languages is high, effective use of modern methods and innovative educational technologies in the educational process will make this process quick and effective. In particular, technological tools are used for every skill of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening and speaking). As the educational system of our country sets itself the goal of educating a well-

rounded, mature and free-thinking person, we urge all future teachers to teach foreign languages to young people by learning modern methods and technologies and using them effectively. we can contribute to the development of our country through excellent teaching.

References:

1. Bekmurodova.U.B. "Using innovative technologies in teaching English" report on the topic., Tashkent 2012.
2. Khatamova N.Q., Mirzayeva M.N. "Interactive used in English language classes methods" (methodical guide), Navoi. 2006, 40 pages
3. Yakubov I. "Methodology of teaching English", (study guide). Tashkent, Sharq publishing house. 2003
4. Ahrorovna, N. N. ., & Marjona, M.. (2021). In Essential Memory Improving Techniques Teaching and Learning Process. "ONLINE - CONFERENCES" PLATFORM, 62–68. Retrieved from <http://papers.online-conferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/589>
5. Saidova, M. U. (2019). Lexical Stylistic Devices and Literary Terms of Figurative Language. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ISSN,22773878.<https://www.ijrte.org/wpcontent/uploads/papers/v8i3S/C10541083S19.pdf>.
6. Sayidova Muhayyo (2021). Semantic analysis of literary terms by literery types in “The concise Oxford Dictionary of literature terms”
", Philology Matters: Vol. 2021 : Iss. 1 , Article 11. DOI: 10.36078/987654486
Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/philolm/vol2021/iss1/11>
7. Rasulov, Z. I. (2010). Principle of contextual analysis elliptical predlozheny (no material of English language). Vestnik Chelyabinskogo Gosudarstvennogo University, (21), 91-94. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/printsip-kontekstualnogo-analiza-ellipticheskikh-predlozheniy-na-materiale-angliyskogo-yazyka/viewer>
8. Kobilova, N. S. (2018). BENEFITS OF USING SONGS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO YOUNG LEARNERS.